

15th

ANNUAL REPORT

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY
RESOURCES
INC.

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for the year ending June 30, 1971

**COUNCIL ON LIBRARY
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INC.**

ONE DUPONT CIRCLE, WASHINGTON, D. C. 20036

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COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
JULY 1, 1970 - JUNE 30, 1971

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COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

The Council on Library Resources, Inc., is an independent nonprofit body incorporated in the District of Columbia with the principal objective of aiding in the solution of library problems. The Council, whose Members also constitute its Board of Directors, maintains its offices in Washington, D. C.

The Council was established in 1956 at the instance of the Ford Foundation with a grant of five million dollars, to be expended over a five-year period, "for the purpose of aiding in the solution of problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular, conducting research in, developing and demonstrating new techniques and methods, and disseminating through any means the results thereof, and for making grants to other institutions and persons for such purposes; and for providing leadership in and wherever appropriate, coordination of efforts (1) to develop the resources and services of libraries and (2) to improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives."

In 1960, in 1967, and again in 1971 the Ford Foundation approved new grants totalling eighteen million dollars to enable the Council to carry forward its programs of research and demonstration toward the solution of library problems.

The Council conducts much of its work through grants or contracts to appropriate organizations or individuals. It welcomes proposals for work in furtherance of its objectives.

INTRODUCTION

The Year 1970-1971

In January 1971 a study prepared for the Carnegie Commission on Higher Education and the Ford Foundation was published,* documenting a trend already apparent to careful observers: the majority of American institutions of higher learning, after a decade of the most rapid growth and development in history, were entering upon a period of economic stress requiring the most prudent financial management. The decline in federal support for higher education, reduced funding by some state governments in reaction to public resistance to higher taxes and to student unrest, rising enrollments and allocations for student aid and minority programs, the decreasing purchasing power of the dollar, increasing salaries—all these, according to the study, were contributing to “the new depression.”

No type of academic institution or any part of it is immune to the effects of this financial squeeze—including the library. A comparable situation is being encountered by public libraries, especially those in urban areas.

It is a situation which might just possibly be manageable if all that was required was maintenance of the *status quo ante*. But the demands upon libraries for services are becoming not only more varied but more sophisticated. One has, for instance, only to think of the growth in use of audiovisual materials, or the call for access to publications from once remote foreign countries, or the need for service to members of previously unserved groups. The increasing rate of publication—of serials as well as monographs—brings with it another set of problems . . . problems of additional purchase funds, increased pressures on cataloging, greater storage requirements. One wonders at times if there is any general realization of how well libraries have done in meeting the pressures put upon them, of how well—in spite of multiplying difficulties—they have succeeded in their primary function of placing in a reader's hands the book or serial he desires.

One wonders also how long the large libraries, using primarily traditional methods of operation, can continue to offer services of

* Earl F. Cheit. *The New Depression in Higher Education, a Study of Financial Conditions at 41 Colleges and Universities*. New York, McGraw Hill Book Company, (1971).

quite remarkable quality in the face of limited resources and increased costs. Some cutbacks in hours of service and in funds for acquisitions and new personnel have already taken place. A period during which it was commonly said that there was a shortage of professional personnel has come rather abruptly to an end, and now we hear talk of an oversupply. Actually, there is not an oversupply of trained librarians; there is just an undersupply of funds with which to employ them.

Automation has been seen as an answer to many of the problems of libraries. It is *beginning* to be an answer, and librarians, like others, will have to take it into consideration as they plan for the future—always bearing in mind that automation is valuable only as it contributes to the library's chief function: service. We have much to learn about its application, and we have much progress to make. Judging from the pattern of development in other fields of technological activity, changes can be expected to come with relative rapidity. We have passed the very first stages and are now seeing the early steps in the development of better equipment and systems and perhaps also a decline in cost.

It is undoubtedly true that library operations can be made more efficient through the judicious use of automation and other technological improvements, through better management, better procedures and systems, and personnel trained in their uses. But we need more than efficiency and economy if libraries and their requirements are not to be disregarded in these difficult times. What seems to be lacking is a constituency of users with a vocal and active appreciation of the role that libraries play in their lives.

Through every available means we must work to produce a greater understanding of the significance of libraries in our society, particularly in every aspect of our educational systems. For today more than ever libraries are the bedrock of education, of cultural and scientific advancement. The library community knows this, of course. But do users? Do those upon whom libraries depend for support?

In the belief that libraries are an irreplaceable asset, the Council on Library Resources during the fiscal year covered by this report allocated \$1,401,982 for the support of 32 new projects and continued or completed work on a number of others. In some cases assistance which cannot be measured in dollars and cents was provided by Council staff.

As in previous years, our dealings with librarians have reinforced our conviction that, in good times or bad, they are a joy to work with. We are much indebted for their helpfulness and their friendship.

FRED C. COLE
President

The Council's Program 1970 - 1971

I ADMINISTRATION AND MANAGEMENT

Academic libraries, like the colleges and universities of which they are a part, find themselves on the horns of an apparently insoluble dilemma—how, on the one hand, to provide more and better services to their clientele with, on the other hand, allotments which are rising much less rapidly than the needs in terms of both the dollars available and what those dollars will buy. Several years ago the Council recognized the approaching crisis and started on a long-range program designed to help libraries make maximum use of the resources available to them. It seemed then, as it does now, that the experience of business and government in utilizing management techniques could be successfully adapted for our libraries.

Research Library Management Earlier reports have related the beginning of the Council's program in this important area with a grant to the Association of Research Libraries (ARL) for a preliminary study of academic library management by Booz, Allen & Hamilton, management consultants.¹ The team was assisted in its work by a joint ARL-American Council on Education (ACE) committee, and the report which ensued suggested a number of areas in which further and specialized studies should be made.

One direct outgrowth of that report was the establishment of the Office of University Library Management Studies within the Association of Research Libraries, cosponsored by the American Council on Education and funded by the Council on Library Resources. On the theory that it is simpler, more economical, and in the end more effective to train a library administrator in management practices than to attempt to do it the other way around, the director of the Office is a professional with experience in business, public, and university libraries. He has received intensive on-the-job training in management practices through working as part of the Booz, Allen & Hamilton team which is conducting the study of the Columbia University Libraries described below. During the coming months the Office, with the guidance of its advisory committee composed of distinguished university administrators and research librarians, will

¹ XIII: 24; XIV: 11-12. Citations in this form refer to the Council's annual reports: for example to the 13th Annual Report, page 24.

develop projects—some of which it will monitor and others carry out itself—for the benefit of university libraries throughout the country. Findings will be disseminated through reports, manuals, conferences, and demonstrations.

A request from Columbia University and the Association of Research Libraries provided the opportunity for taking the next step in the logical development of the program—a case study of some management aspects of a large university library. To meet this request the Council contracted with Booz, Allen & Hamilton to conduct a study of the organization and staffing of the Columbia University Libraries. As with the earlier Council grants in this area, the work is supervised by a joint ARL-ACE committee. Columbia's library system is felt to be a useful object of study because it offers the operational complexities, the service capabilities, and the financial problems characteristic of most large academic libraries. Further, the Columbia Libraries are deeply involved in the development of computer-based record systems and in regional and national cooperative programs designed to extend access to resources and to promote coordination of resource development and bibliographic control. While the study has been focused on the Columbia Libraries and their specific needs, it is believed that it will be of general interest and assistance to other institutions in developing projects that will help them prepare plans of organization and staffing matched to their own objectives and needs.

Study of Library Economics The Council during the preceding fiscal year contracted with Mathematica, Princeton, New Jersey, for the first phase of a study of the economics of university library operations.² Such a study can assist academic libraries in their internal planning, aid them in estimating future financial requirements, and better enable them to justify their fair share of available funds. The Council this year contracted for the completion of the work.

User Behavior The library of the University of Lancaster in England has for several years been seeking to appraise the role of the library in an academic community and has established a Library Research Unit for the purpose.³ The first phase of this management research project (1967-69) concentrated on the provision of library services and led the library to make significant changes of policy in the areas of circulation, duplication of stock, and binding. Believing that the second phase of the work will be

²XIV: 12.

³Activities at Lancaster are described in "Library Research at the University of Lancaster," by A. Graham Mackenzie, *Library Association Record* 73: 90-92. May 1971.

even more useful beyond the project site itself, the Council has made a grant to the University for an analysis which attempts to establish user response to procedural or technological changes at the Library. The investigators hope to discover and identify information about the factors that tend to encourage or discourage the use of available services, to pinpoint the factors within the librarian's power to influence, and to learn how the impact of proposed changes in library and information services can be predicted.

The Council has joined with the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) in providing funds for a study of library users—and nonusers—in another environment. Brooklyn's crowded Bedford-Stuyvesant area, with a population which is 70 percent black and 11 percent Puerto Rican, has severe poverty problems. Hardy R. Franklin, a practicing librarian working toward a doctorate at the Rutgers Graduate School of Library Service, has been seeking to ascertain whether the nature and extent of library use and nonuse can be seen as reflections of socioeconomic characteristics of the residents, and to study the similarities and differences between and within these characteristics. The information gathered in this study has useful implications for planning library service to communities with disadvantaged populations.

Public Library Goals No group is more aware than librarians themselves of the need to revitalize and recast the role of the public libraries. Yesterday's patterns of service reflected the requirements of a very different world; they must be remodeled in terms of today's imperatives. Thus the Council and the National Endowment for the Humanities were pleased to make matching grants to the American Library Association's Public Library Association for a preliminary evaluative study of the goals and services of public libraries. The study is a forerunner of a full-scale investigation of the effect on libraries of altering urban and social conditions as well as of broadening opportunities for higher education.

Dallas Public Library The Dallas Public Library will in September 1971 embark on a two-year program to investigate the effectiveness of the public library as a center for independent study directed toward a two-year college education. The project focuses on the College Entrance Examination Board's College Level Examination Program (CLEP), which offers individuals who are unable or unwilling to attend regular class sessions an opportunity to receive credit for courses on the basis of examination alone. College Information Centers, to be established at five of the Dallas Public branches serving differing socioeconomic communities, will provide information about CLEP and about the aca-

demographic programs of area colleges and universities. Southern Methodist University is actively participating in the project, and other institutions of higher education in the region have indicated their willingness to cooperate. Tutorial and workshop services as well as guides for the subject fields included in CLEP, prepared by Southern Methodist faculty members, will be available at the libraries to adults seeking self-education and academic recognition. This program—which has been funded by the College Entrance Examination Board, the National Endowment for the Humanities, and the Council on Library Resources—has important implications for public libraries everywhere.

Model R & D Unit The *14th Annual Report* described the long-felt requirement for a unit, based within an active library, to test the usefulness of the systematic application of research and development to library matters.⁴ With the assistance of the Council such a unit was established at the Joint University Libraries in Nashville, Tennessee, in July of 1970. During the year R & D techniques have been brought to bear on some common library problems—among them personnel policies, performance data, program budgeting, and management by objectives. As the unit grows in expertise and experience, it is expected to publish reports and studies that will be helpful to other academic libraries.

Business School Libraries Guidelines for administrators of college and university business school libraries were the subject of discussion at a recent annual meeting of the Special Libraries Association. This led to the appointment of a Committee on Standards for Collegiate Schools of Business, which in turn prompted numerous requests from deans, faculty members, and librarians for help in determining what are adequate library resources and the incident cost. Useful information was lacking, and to meet the need the Council this year made a grant to the American Association of Collegiate Schools of Business for a survey of their libraries. Data gathered from 109 accredited and 118 nonaccredited members of the Association and published by it in report form provide information on expenditures and budgets, library staffs, nature of the business collections, and supporting services.⁵ The report is a useful tool for collegiate business school administrators and others in this special area who wish to determine how their libraries stand in relation to others in the field.

⁴ XIV: 13.

⁵ American Association of Collegiate Schools of Business. *Special Library Resources Study 1970-71*. St. Louis, Missouri, The Association. (iv, 55) 1. Processed. 28cms.

A State Research Depository Library The North Carolina State Board of Higher Education in its 1968 report recommended that a study be made to determine the feasibility of a central research library facility which could serve as a depository for materials from various libraries within the state. The following year the Council made a grant for the study, which was cosponsored by the North Carolina State Library, the State Board of Higher Education, the North Carolina Library Association, and the North Carolina State Board of Education.⁶ This year the Council received a final report on the project.⁷ The report recommends that the facility be established and that it be part of a projected broad network of cooperating libraries. The State Library Board has "accepted both the concept of the North Carolina Services Network and the logic of supporting it from state funds."

A Manual of Systems Design An active interest in systems analysis and design as related to library operations at Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute led Edward A. Chapman, Director of Libraries, and his colleague, Paul L. St. Pierre, to prepare a manual for the information of their own staff. They also gave courses on the subject for other librarians in the region. From these activities has developed a book, published this year, for the preparation of which the Council made a grant.⁸ The manual, based on the "total systems" concept, provides guidelines for analyzing and evaluating already existing operating systems and for designing improved or new ones. The intent of a systems study, the authors point out, need not necessarily be computerization.

Archivists: A Plan for the 1970s The membership of the Society of American Archivists, now approximately 2,300, more than doubled during the past decade. While the increase is gratifying, it has led to problems. In addition to the growing volume and complexity of the Society's work, changes are occurring in the nature and character of the profession itself. This winter the Council made a grant toward the expenses of a committee which,

⁶ XIII: 30.

⁷ *The Next Step for North Carolina Libraries: A Libraries Services Network*. The Report of a Feasibility Study of the North Carolina Libraries Services Network Sponsored by North Carolina State Library, State Board of Higher Education, North Carolina Library Association, State Board of Education. Richard H. Leach, Study Director. Raleigh, North Carolina State Board of Higher Education, January 1971. iv, 18 p. 28cms.

⁸ XI: 16. Edward A. Chapman, Paul L. St. Pierre, and John Lubans, Jr. *Library Systems Analysis Guidelines*. New York, Wiley-Interscience, A Division of John Wiley & Sons, Inc., (1970). xiii, 226 p.

after studying proposed organizational changes and the programs and goals of the Society, will develop a long-range program for the 1970s.

During recent years remarkable gains have been made in the appreciation of archives and an understanding of the need for their proper preservation, but the profession's literature is still quantitatively slight. So that planners of buildings for archival collections may profit from the experience of the past several decades, the Council made a grant to the Society in 1967 for the preparation of a reader on the planning of archives and records center buildings.⁹ The reader was published this fiscal year.¹⁰ The compiler is Victor Gondos, Jr., who is both an archivist and a professionally qualified architect.

Library Lighting Views vary considerably as to what is the proper level of lighting for libraries. As previously reported, the Council made a grant to the Association of Research Libraries for a study of the complex subject by Keyes D. Metcalf, Librarian Emeritus of Harvard College and elder statesman of library building consultants.¹¹ Mr. Metcalf's study has now been published.¹² In preparing it he had the assistance of an advisory committee as well as of more than fifty consultants.

II THE PROFESSION

The Council on Library Resources shares the opinion that—fine buildings, great collections, complete applications of modern technology notwithstanding—a library is as good as the people who staff it. For too long now this essential component of potential strength has been under-emphasized in the search for ways to help libraries do the job required of them in successfully meeting the changing and growing needs of an increasingly diverse society.

The profession apparently has failed to attract and keep in its ranks enough young people of high ability and to provide them as

⁹ XII: 11.

¹⁰ Victor Gondos, Jr., compiler. *Reader for Archives and Records Center Buildings*. (No place), Committee on Archival Buildings and Equipment, The Society of American Archivists, (1970). viii, 127 p.

¹¹ XII: 21.

¹² Keyes D. Metcalf. *Library Lighting*. Washington, D. C., The Association of Research Libraries, 1970. viii, 99 p.

well as more experienced librarians with sufficient rewards in terms of salary and opportunities for advancement or self-enrichment. Since 1968 the Council has been engaged in two programs devoted to this aspect of library work.¹³ It is hoped that by highlighting characteristic features of library staff structures, ways will be suggested of providing the outlets and opportunities which the profession needs.

Economics of Academic Librarianship Last year's annual report told of the preliminary statistical survey of salaries in 249 academic libraries, conducted by Donald F. Cameron and Peggy Heim, part-time consultants for the Council.

Dr. Cameron was director of the Rutgers University Libraries until his retirement; Dr. Heim is the former staff economist of the American Association of University Professors and now serves as Director of the Planning Center for the South Carolina Independent Colleges. The report resulting from their study has been published¹⁴ and confirms the fact that librarians fare less well than others in comparable fields in terms of financial remuneration. It points up as well the equally important—and discouraging—fact that in librarianship as the profession is now constituted there is very little room at the top. Less than ten percent of all librarians ever achieve the position of assistant, associate, or full director.

During the year covered by this annual report a larger and statistically more representative group of colleges and universities was surveyed to ascertain, first, whether the general pattern of increase in earnings pertained in the academic library world, and, second, whether anything useful could be learned concerning the structure of the profession by asking more detailed questions about the “specialists”—bibliographers, collection builders, curators, language experts, accountants, personnel officers, computer experts, statisticians, etc., etc.

A report based on this second survey is in preparation and will be published in the 1971-1972 fiscal year.

Fellowship Program The Council has this year continued its Fellowship Program, designed to enable a limited number of promising mid-career librarians from the United States and Canada to improve their competence in the substantive, administrative, and/or technical aspects of their profession.¹⁵ The

¹³ XII: 35; XIII: 28, 41-42; XIV: 43-46.

¹⁴ Peggy Heim and Donald F. Cameron. *The Economics of Librarianship in College and University Libraries, 1969-70. A Sample Survey of Compensations.* (Washington), Council on Library Resources, Inc., July 1970. 20 p.

¹⁵ XII: 35; XIII: 41-42; XIV: 44-46.

awards do not cover salaries but are for such items as travel, per diem for living expenses, and supplies and equipment incident to a fellow's program. A fellow's salary while on leave is expected to be met by his parent institution. Grants are not made to those primarily concerned with working toward an advanced degree as this is considered outside the program's intent.

Louis B. Wright, Vice-Chairman of the Council's Board of Directors and Director Emeritus of the Folger Shakespeare Library, is chairman of the Fellowship Committee. Other members include: William S. Dix, Librarian of Princeton University; Robert Vosper, Librarian of the University of California at Los Angeles; and ex officio, Fred C. Cole, President of the Council; Foster E. Mohrhardt, Senior Program Officer; and Edith M. Lesser, Secretary and Treasurer of the Council.

This spring fellowships were awarded to 18 librarians, bringing to 53 the total given since the program's inception three years ago. The new fellows and their projects are:

Albert G. Anderson, Jr., Librarian, Worcester Polytechnic Institute, Worcester, Massachusetts. A study to determine the tangible and intangible benefits to be gained by the faculties and student bodies of institutions in cooperating library organizations.

Howard L. Applegate, Director, George Arents Research Library, Syracuse University. To study current practices of library governance and internal management techniques and procedures, as well as the role of libraries in university governance and administrative systems, among significant university research libraries in the United States.

Clifton Brock, Associate University Librarian, University of North Carolina. To conduct comparative research on the patterns of publication, distribution, and bibliographic control of U.S. and British government documents.

Betty Duvall, Assistant Dean for Instructional Resources, Florissant Valley Community College, St. Louis, Missouri. To identify trends in curricular innovation in community college instructional programs and the implication for library collection building which follows.

Jane G. Flener, Assistant Director of Libraries, Indiana University. An investigation of patterns to involve staff in many kinds of decisions in large libraries, with special attention to results.

Yates M. Forbis, Librarian, Dickinson College, Carlisle, Pennsylvania. To study the extent to which joint library projects in selected small college cooperatives have affected curricular changes and development among the member institutions.

Clyde L. Haselden, Librarian, Lafayette College, Easton, Pennsylvania. A study of cooperation among college libraries to discover effective ways for improvement and expansion of the recently established cooperative efforts of The Lehigh Valley Association of Independent College Libraries.

Donald D. Hendricks, Director, South Central Regional Medical Library Program, Dallas, Texas. To study and reflect upon the present trend toward library networks as one solution to the problems of library resources and services.

Carol F. Ishimoto, Senior Cataloger, Harvard College Library. To conduct a fact-finding study to examine the impact of the National Program for Acquisitions and Cataloging of the Library of Congress on the internal technical operations of a selected group of university libraries, with the primary objective of investigating how university libraries are dealing with the changes resulting from shared cataloging.

David A. Kronick, Librarian, Medical School at San Antonio, University of Texas. Further development of a study on the history of the earlier scientific periodical press as a source for the history of science and technology and as a background for the development of the periodical as a primary medium of scientific record and information dissemination.

John Lubans, Jr., Assistant Director for Public Services, University of Colorado Libraries. To continue studying patterns of academic library use and nonuse and the effect library orientation and library-use presentations have and could have on these.

Howard Messman, Mathematics Librarian, University of Illinois Library. To research the need and ways to improve bibliographic tools in the literature of mathematics for both patrons and librarians.

T. H. Milby, Science Librarian, University of Oklahoma. An investigation of graduate or upper level literature courses taught in departments of life science of selected universities.

Theodore P. Peck, Chief, Reference Services Department, University Libraries, University of Minnesota. To study the training programs now underway in Great Britain for technologists in industry and for potential research and development personnel in the natural sciences and engineering, preparatory to setting up a similar program at the University of Minnesota.

James A. Riddles, Director of Libraries, University of the Pacific. To investigate administrative techniques that have been successful on the medium-sized college campus in redirecting teaching objectives and techniques to utilize more fully the resources and services of the library.

Frederick E. Smith, Law Librarian, University of California at Los Angeles. To investigate and evaluate the legislative and administrative measures which have been adopted in this country and abroad to facilitate the development of a national information resource and its exploitation through computer technology, and to make proposals based on these investigations and evaluations.

Morton Snowwhite, Librarian, Newark College of Engineering, Newark, New Jersey. A comparative study of cataloging in academic libraries.

Richard L. Snyder, Director of Libraries, Drexel University. To study the quantitative aspects of administration in technological university libraries.

III NATIONAL LIBRARY SERVICE

The idealized situation, with all major libraries linked and hence constituting one great universal library to which all readers would have access, has been mentioned many times. The day of the "one great library" is still far off, but some essential first steps toward it are being taken.

Basic to achievement of the ideal is the existence of a central source of experience, authority, and prestige to lead in coordinating the development of library resources and services in an orderly and economical fashion. Duplicated effort and incompatibility among independently developed programs and the attendant waste of effort and money must be avoided. What better source of prestigious authority in the United States than the three national libraries working in cooperation? The magnitude of their operations gives them a momentum, the size of their collections an impulsion to meet the widespread demand for their bibliographic services.

National Libraries Task Force It was toward this end that the Library of Congress, the National Library of Medicine, and the National Agricultural Library in 1967 established the National Libraries Task Force on Automation and Other Cooperative Services. Since all the principals and alternates on the Task Force have responsible positions with their respective libraries and are unable to devote full time to Task Force activities, the Council has included on its staff since 1968 two systems specialists to work with the Task Force.¹⁶

The Task Force has achieved agreement on standards for some of the bibliographic information to be represented in automated systems, and is working on the coordination of present and future automation of the libraries' acquisitions systems.

National Serials Data Program Periodicals and other serials are essential to research and hence constitute one of the most important elements in library collections. Because titles and other data elements are subject to frequent change and require constant updating, they are difficult to control. As computers have the capability of providing an exhaustive record of serial publications which can be constantly updated, the Joint Committee on the Union List of Serials in 1967 proposed a National Serials Data Program that would lead to a computerized central store of serials data. The Council joined with the three national

¹⁶ XII: 14; XIII: 17; XIV: 23.

libraries and the National Science Foundation in providing support for the first phase of the project, during which development of a comprehensive set of data elements and other work was accomplished.¹⁷ This in turn led to a pilot project, conducted by the Association of Research Libraries under the auspices of the Task Force, to clarify the policies and mechanisms required for a national serials system.¹⁸ Financial support came principally from the National Agricultural Library, with additional amounts of money and services contributed by the other two national libraries and by the Council. The pilot project has just been concluded and has contributed another important step toward development of a national serials data base. The three national libraries have agreed to develop and manage future work on the National Serials Data Program, and to seek funding for it.

Standard Serial Number Any serials system requires that each publication, or title, be uniquely identified to avoid confusion.¹⁹ For an automated system this requirement is absolute. Out of this need has come the Standard Serial Number (SSN), developed by a subcommittee of the American National Standards Institute's Committee Z39, Standardization in the Field of Library Work, Documentation, and Related Publishing Practices. The SSN is a unique eight-digit number assigned permanently to each periodical, yearbook, or other serial. The Serials Pilot Project experimented with the assignment of the SSN and the maintenance of the machine registry of the assigned number in its retrospective file, while the Library of Congress has been experimenting with assignment of SSNs to newly established titles.

The assignment of code numbers as a continuing activity should be the responsibility of a central authority, and the Library of Congress has agreed to undertake this for the United States, subject to the availability of funds. The American National Standards Institute has approved and published the standard for the SSN, and this spring a plenary session of Technical Committee 46, International Standards Organization, recommended adoption of the American Standard Serial Number as the international standard.

Committee Z39 American National Standards Institute The Standard Serial Number is but one of the numerous projects with which Committee Z39's various subcommittees have been concerned during the year. Among others have been standards for the format for communication of bibliographical

¹⁷ XII: 14-15.

¹⁸ XIV: 22-23.

¹⁹ XIV: 23-24.

information on magnetic tape, for periodical title abbreviations, for transliteration of Arabic and several other non-Roman alphabet languages, and for proof corrections. When a Z39 subcommittee has formulated a standard it is forwarded to the parent American National Standards Institute for approval and promulgation. The national organization also represents the United States in the International Standards Organization, thereby giving American library interests a voice when international standards are set. The Council and the National Science Foundation, recognizing the importance of adequate standards and their acceptance, have provided the funds for the work of Z39 since 1962.²⁰

MARC Machine readable cataloging developed from a long and series of Council grants to the Library of Congress for **RECON** work in the field of automation which would have national implications.²¹ It supplies to subscribing libraries and networks, in machine-readable language on magnetic tape, bibliographic data for monograph titles cataloged at the Library of Congress in standard format. MARC, the first library development of its kind in the world, was initially limited to current U.S. monographs in the English language. The MARC Distribution Service is now an ongoing activity with coverage extended to all English language monographs cataloged at the Library. A MARC format for serials has been devised, as have formats for single-sheet maps and for films, with work on formats for sound recordings, audio-visual materials, and manuscripts under way.

Desirably, cataloging information on monographs in English processed prior to the advent of MARC and on monographs in foreign languages should also be available in machine-readable form. It is an immense task, in terms of both the number of titles involved and the technical innovations needed, but a start was made in August 1969 with the inception of a RECON (Retrospective Conversion) pilot project, designed to test the feasibility and ascertain the probable cost of massive retrospective conversion.²² The project, which is drawing to a close, has been supported by grants from the Council and the U.S. Office of Education, as well as by the Library's own funds.

The RECON plan anticipated the conversion of 85,000 catalog records to machine-readable form. At last report about half that number had been converted; however, the Library of Congress has

²⁰ XIV: 37-38 and earlier annual reports.

²¹ XIII: 12, 14-17; XIV: 22, 24.

²² Progress reports of the RECON Pilot Project have appeared in the June and September 1970 and March 1971 issues of the *Journal of Library Automation*.

committed itself to completion of the work. Valuable knowledge about different techniques has been gained as the task force experimented with titles in foreign languages, various approaches to editing and microfilming, input devices, and format recognition—a technique which the Library and others have been developing since 1969. Format recognition allows the computer to process unedited bibliographic records by analyzing character sequences for key terms and significant punctuation, spacing, and other clues to determine the proper identification of the data fields. When completely operational it should eliminate substantial portions of the manual editing process and thus reduce the costs of creating machine-readable records.

Cataloging in Publication It is ninety-five years since Justin Winsor, then Librarian of the Boston Public Library and later of Harvard College, and Max Müller, an assistant curator at the Bodleian Library, independently conceived in slightly differing forms the idea of supplying bibliographical information along with the published book. Such a practice could reduce costs to libraries by providing them with at least the basic cataloging information at the moment of the book's arrival, thus eliminating the need to catalog it themselves or obtain the information elsewhere and, incidentally, making the book more quickly available to the reader. The idea never wholly died, and in 1958-59 the Library of Congress, with the support of the Council, experimented with what was then called "cataloging in source."²⁸ Some 1,200 publications of 157 publishers were so cataloged during the experiment. Although most of the participating publishers expressed a willingness to go on if the practice benefited libraries and if a representative group of libraries wished for continuance, the project was terminated after eight months. The chief reasons given for ending it were cost to the publishers and the Library, and the prevalence of errors in 42 percent of the cataloged titles. However, the errors were usually slight and were occasioned by frequent changes of imprint and/or collation after the cataloging, which was done from page proofs, had been completed.

In the decade which has passed since that experiment, renewed interest has been expressed in the idea of pre-publication cataloging. On the recommendation of the Joint Committee of the American Book Publishers Council (now the Association of American Publishers) and the Resources and Technical Services Division of the American Library Association, and at the request of the Library of

²⁸ II: 15-18; IV: 24-25; X: 18. The Council's practice of reproducing a catalog card in its annual report—this year located at the bottom of page 48—began at this time, first appearing in its 2nd Annual Report for the period ending June 30, 1958.

Congress, a Council staff member this year studied the feasibility of a new program.

This spring the National Endowment for the Humanities and the Council joined in making a substantial grant to the Library of Congress for support of the Cataloging in Publication program, as it is now called, for two years. The U.S. Office of Education and the National Science Foundation have also indicated their potential interest in supporting the project.

The Library has established procedures which are expected to obviate the occasions of error that occurred in the earlier experiment. The catalogers will work from galley, not page proofs, and the turn-around time for the pre-publication cataloging will be a week instead of twenty-four hours. In addition, the cataloging entry to be printed in the book will be limited to author, title, bibliographical notes, subject headings, and classification symbols (in both Library of Congress and Dewey Decimal systems), and International Standard Book Number. Omitted will be those elements—pagination and date of publication—most subject to error in the 1958-59 program.

Starting with a portion of the output of the major American publishers, the Library hopes that by the end of two years it will be able to supply the data for most of the titles—some 30,000 in number—published each year by the U. S. book trade.

United States Book Exchange In another action affecting the national library community, the Council has made a grant to the United States Book Exchange (USBE) to enable it to meet unexpected needs and strengthen its operation by the employment of additional personnel for a one-year period. The USBE, a private nonprofit organization, was established in 1948 for the purpose of receiving surplus publications from libraries and redistributing them to other libraries upon request. It has been almost wholly self-supporting since its establishment, deriving its income largely from the handling fees paid by member libraries. During the past several years, despite prudent management, the USBE has experienced difficulties resulting from such factors as increased costs relative to earnings and a reduction in the size of individual orders caused by restricted library budgets. The downward trend led to a cutback in staff, which in turn affected the quality and speed of USBE's unique service to libraries and thus its income. During the period of the grant USBE intends to take various actions—including an increase in fees and revision of governance—which will help to put it once again on a solid foundation.

Library Technology Program This year the Council brought to an end its twelve years of support toward the general operations of the American Library Association's Library Technology Program (LTP). It was felt that LTP had developed to the point where it could be independent of Council grants for basic purposes. Established in 1958 upon the Council's initiative, LTP has provided a continuous program of testing and standardizing of equipment, supplies, and systems, and of collaboration with industry in the development of improved or new products for libraries.²⁴ In this connection, LTP's work received recognition in June 1971 when in London it was awarded a commemorative scroll as a runner-up for the 1970 Robinson Medal, awarded biennially by the (British) Library Association for "originality and inventive ability . . . in connection with devising new and improved methods of library technology and any aspect of library administration." LTP's honor came for its work in developing, with extended assistance from the Council, the SE-LIN labeling system for books, patented in seven countries. More than 3,000 SE-LIN systems are now in use by librarians around the world.

It would be difficult to single out the most important or significant projects undertaken by LTP. All of them—from the testing of library chairs to the evaluation of microform readers—have been motivated by the desire to promote efficiency and to save libraries money by providing them with needed information on the procedures and equipment which consume such a large portion of every library's budget. The Council will continue to make separate grants for some investigations, such as the one which resulted in a 37-page paper on "Permanent and Durable Catalog Cards," prepared by the Chicago Paper Testing Laboratory and published in the January 1971 issue of *Library Technology Reports*, LTP's bimonthly subscription service. LTP also reports many of its findings in regular columns of library journals. In addition it responds, without charge, to some hundreds of individual telephone and mail inquiries—some from abroad—each year.

LTP supports as well a publishing program of technical manuals for the library profession. The latest of these is *The Evaluation of Micropublications, A Handbook for Librarians*, by Allen B. Veaner, Assistant Director of the Stanford University Libraries.²⁵

²⁴ III: 38-39 and subsequent annual reports.

²⁵ Chicago, American Library Association, *Library Technology Program*, (1971). xii, 59 p.

IV AUTOMATION

There are times when one would wish there were a national superbody to control the direction and the funding of important new developments. The application of automation to libraries is a case in point. Widespread agreement exists that the advanced and developing technology has a good deal to offer libraries in terms of increased efficiency, better service to users, and eventual reduction of operating costs. A similar level of accord is lacking relative to the best utilization of the technology in order to produce the desired effects. This has resulted in a proliferation of individual developments at a number of institutions, each project costly in terms of funds and manpower—both in short supply—and with insufficient consideration given to eventual compatibility with developments in other libraries or networks.

The Council does not pretend to know the answers to the questions implicit in the problem; nor, if it did, would it be or wish to be in a position to force its opinions on the rest of the library community. It has, however, for its own guidance developed a set of hypotheses from which it has drawn the conclusions that govern its current grant-making in the area of library automation.

The Council believes that only the largest of our libraries will, in the foreseeable future, be able to afford automated systems dedicated to their exclusive use. Most libraries should be thinking in terms of consortia and similar compacts in order to avail themselves at reasonable cost of the benefits automation can provide. And, in our concern for the libraries of the present we will not ignore the necessity to see to it that basic research and experimentation are undertaken that will provide the foundations for the libraries of tomorrow.

Within these parameters, and with the limited funds available to the Council for this one activity, support will be given to only a few of the most promising projects which come to us. Naturally, a number of judgments enter into each selection made: significant are judgments on the experience and record of the proponents, on the amount of support provided by the institution's administration, on the feasibility of the plan insofar as this can be determined from a proposal and site visits. Not every project selected for support will turn out as successfully as had been originally hoped, but all will have served a useful purpose in making us and others much more aware of what can be realistically expected of automation.

Project Intrex The program of Information Transfer Experiments (Intrex) which started at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology in 1965 has as its objective the development

of innovative methods, utilizing new technology or combinations of it, to bring under bibliographic control and improve access to the ever growing mass of books, periodicals, reports, and other records at M.I.T. and elsewhere. The Council has been interested in the experimental program from its inception and made the first of a series of grants to it in 1967.²⁶

This year the project's Catalog Input Group completed the indexing necessary to bring the data base to 18,000 documents, of which more than 17,000 have been keyed and almost 16,000 processed into the computer store. Work has begun on an expanded and updated Augmented Catalog Manual intended to provide full documentation on its present status. The Augmented Catalog differs from the conventional library catalog in that it contains a greater number of catalog entry points and, because it is held in direct-access storage devices, is capable of rapid and flexible manipulation by the user. The major portion of the requisite hardware and software development has been completed and project staff is concentrating its attention on appraisal and refinement of the system through user experiments in both controlled and uncontrolled environments. A start has also been made on an economic model of the system in order to obtain needed information concerning costs of utilization.

A model transitional library developed by the project is now functioning within M.I.T.'s Barker Engineering Library, with services based on the new technologies and new uses of old technologies alongside, and integrated into, traditional services.

University of Chicago Library The University of Chicago Library during the period 1966-1970 developed an extensive computer-based bibliographic data processing system with assistance from the National Science Foundation. In view of the Library's experience, the Council and the National Endowment for the Humanities—as noted in the previous annual report—made matching grants to the Library in partial support of a five-year program for the continuing investigation, development, and testing of a computerized library data management system.²⁷

The functions of the Library Data Management System include complex computer file organization, maintenance, indexing, query and response, and reporting activities. Thus the first objective under the grant will be the development of efficient computer software systems capable of supporting these functions.

The second objective will be to make practical use of this software system in a number of library file-related operations, several

²⁶ IX: 10; XI: 14-15; XII: 13; XIII: 18-19; XIV: 15-16, 30-31.

²⁷ XIV: 31.

of which represent major library functions—for example, circulation.

The new development will provide better means of access to bibliographic data in very large files and will allow more sophisticated use of these data bases by providing a multiple-key access capability—i.e., direct access to records by a variety of keys such as author, title, call number, subject, etc.

Among the remaining and as yet unfunded tasks of the basic five-year program are the development of a serials access and control system, a library performance monitoring system, and library operations studies. A longer-range goal is to make it possible for the system to link up with such sources of specialized information as the National Library of Medicine's MEDLARS, the Chemical Abstract Service, and other discipline-based systems.

Ohio College Library Center The Ohio College Library Center (OCLC), in Columbus, is developing a computerized regional library system. As of June 30, 1971 an off-line system for catalog card production was in operation, serving 40 colleges and universities in the state and, on a trial basis, the University of Pittsburgh. Options for customized card production in the system make it possible to produce cards in thousands of format and content combinations. The off-line system is the precursor of a MARC-based on-line system which was expected to become operational in July 1971. This system will produce cards for member libraries, provide an on-line union catalog of resources in Ohio academic libraries, and serve as a communications system for querying the catalog and requesting inter-library loans.

A year ago the Council made a small grant to OCLC, supplementing funds from the Center's own budget and from the U.S. Office of Education.²⁸ This spring the Council prepared to make a new and considerably larger grant which would assist the Center to develop systems for serials control, technical processing, remote catalog access and circulation control, and bibliographical information retrieval. This grant too will augment funds made available by the Office of Education.

New England Library Network The Council made the first of a series of grants to the New England Board of Higher Education for the New England Library Network (NELINET) in 1966.²⁹ That was for the development of specifications of the projected network. Since then, with continued assistance from the Council, NELINET has become a computer-

²⁸ XIV: 25-26.

²⁹ XI: 12-14; XII: 12; XIII: 17-18; XIV: 25.

based regional library technical processing center supplying to the member libraries of the New England State Universities, from MARC tapes, custom catalog card sets, spine labels and book labels. The University of Vermont and the University of New Hampshire are, in turn, using NELINET services to process books for other libraries in their states.

NELINET has the potential for increasing its services in due time. It has the capability now for serving many other libraries and is actively seeking more members. In view of this, the Council has this year made a grant which enables NELINET to obtain the information it needs to make operational changes in the present system in order to accommodate new members, and to develop methods for integrating into its system the input of local cataloging data not in the Library of Congress' MARC record. The grant will also allow for the compilation of statistics on academic library growth in New England as a planning aid. Comprehensive statistics for all of the 255 academic libraries in the six-state region have not hitherto been available.

Criteria for Quality Control A Council-supported project of the Federation of American Societies for Experimental Biology which attempted to develop extrinsic criteria for the selection of journal articles for inclusion in science abstracting services and other information systems on the basis of merit has been completed and a report published in the Federation's *Proceedings*.³⁰

Journal of Library Automation The Council has concluded its contribution to the establishment and support of the *Journal of Library Automation*, official publication of the Information Science and Automation Division of the American Library Association.³¹ The quarterly, established in 1968, has won its place in the literature with its articles in germane areas of library activity by both American and foreign contributors.

V MICROFORMS

After a lengthy period of slow growth, microform technology is experiencing a burst of development and application accompanied

³⁰ XIII: 28. Raymund L. Zwemer. "Identification of Journal Characteristics Useful in Improving Input and Output of a Retrieval System." *Federation (of American Societies for Experimental Biology) Proceedings*. 29: 1595-1604. September-October 1970.

³¹ XI: 15-16; XII: 11-12.

by extravagant predictions of mushrooming markets and by high rates of bankruptcy, merger, and realignment of companies providing microform products and services. Publishers have viewed with interest the progress of micropublishing ventures, especially the high reduction microform library packages being developed and marketed by two major companies, while trying to decide whether to leap into the business themselves. The Council too has been watching developments carefully, concentrating its efforts in the microform arena on consulting services to libraries and related institutions and on the investigation and development of microform catalog applications. The latter is particularly appropriate at a time when:

- Librarians are more than ever concerned about the physical safety of card catalogs;
- More and more bibliographic information is computer-stored and therefore amenable to outputting through computer output microfilm (COM) equipment;
- Much new and innovative microform reading equipment is coming onto the market;
- The necessity for libraries to reduce costs makes the relatively inexpensive union catalogs in microform a significant possibility for implementing the bibliographic aspects of inter-library loan; and
- The costs of conventional publishing continue to increase.

Tulane Catalog A grant from the Council offered an opportunity for an experiment at the Tulane University Library for the COM-production of a short-title catalog and the testing of its acceptance by librarians and library users.⁸² The catalog covers about 80 percent of the Library's books and periodicals and is an inexpensive by-product of its automated circulation system. A main entry catalog only, it lists books usually under authors and periodicals under their titles.

At the end of this experiment three important conclusions were reported:

- A microfilm catalog *per se* is acceptable to most users. In fact, many users during this experiment were enthusiastic about the technique and urged that it be further developed.
- Existing microfilm reading equipment is, at best, marginally durable for use by the public with little or no instruction or supervision.
- A catalog with quite limited bibliographic data is not an acceptable guide to the library: library staff and other knowledgeable users are frustrated by its incompleteness, and the bibliographically unsophisticated are unaware of its limitations.

⁸² XIV: 30.

Despite the limited success of the experiments, the principal investigator feels that the acceptance given this microform catalog warrants further research and development in the area.

Rice University Catalog Another experiment in microfilm cataloging was concluded this spring at Rice University. The intent there was to prepare on microfilm a union catalog of the collections at a number of academic institutions in the region. This project, like that at Tulane, was closely monitored. Some parts of the program went very well, but technologically some blind alleys were discovered, and it has been concluded that the approach taken is not practical.

New York Public Library The problem of the worn public catalog of the Research Libraries of the New York Public Library (NYPL) has been a matter of concern for many years.³³ Many of the cards in the catalog, which has been in use for more than seventy years, are badly deteriorated. Several years ago studies supported by the Council indicated that the various solutions proposed would cost from \$1 to \$2 million. More recent estimates place the cost much higher. This represents a real dilemma for an institution already in financial difficulties.

This spring the Council made a grant to the Library to determine the feasibility of microfilming the retrospective catalog for purposes of preservation and user access. A relatively small segment of the public card catalog will be replaced by a microfilm version. User acceptance, mechanical feasibility of the microfilm reading machines, and the techniques of administration of the service will be investigated in this experiment. It will also test out production and use of microfilm copies of the library's computer-based book catalog supplements and authority lists. The library's card catalogs receive exceptionally heavy use, but the problems resulting from wear are not and will not be unique to it; what is learned will be useful to other libraries. A member of the Council staff will be a consultant to the experiment.

Micropublishing at Dartmouth Like many other institutions, Dartmouth College contains in its library manuscripts and rare printed editions of considerable scholarly interest. Among these are the European travel journals of George Ticknor and his wife, Anna Eliot Ticknor; a collection of pamphlets on the subject of slavery formed by Chief Justice Salmon P. Chase and a contemporary, Senator John P. Hale; the papers of August Saint-Gaudens, the sculptor; and the Arctic expedition diaries of Vilhjal-

³³ X: 43; XIII: 32-33.

mur Stefansson, supplementing material in the Canadian National Archives.

While the interest in such material is largely limited to the specialist, it is in general desirable that it be made more readily accessible. The production of facsimiles and of editions of the texts by normal letterpress printing is too expensive to be contemplated, but useful results might be accomplished by publication of small editions in microform, accompanied by booklet guides.

The Council has made a grant to the Dartmouth College Library to set up such a project on a trial basis. Dartmouth's experience may encourage other libraries with rare and unique materials to undertake similar publishing projects, perhaps in collaboration with their university presses. Such copying projects also offer protection against complete loss of the content in the event of fire or other disaster.

VI PRESERVATION OF LIBRARY MATERIALS

The problems of deterioration and the conservation of library materials have been of concern to the Council since its inception.³⁴ During its early years it sponsored various research projects relating to the causes and extent of the deterioration problem and possible remedies—the development of specifications for permanent and durable book papers, for example.

Barrow Research Laboratory It soon became apparent, however, that there was much to be gained by the development of a facility which would give its full attention to these matters, and in 1961 the Council established the W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory. CLR has continued its support of the Laboratory through the years and has shared in the control and direction of its work. Of late the Council has encouraged the Laboratory to undertake work under contract with other nonprofit organizations having like interests. It has, in consequence, performed work for the American Library Association on specifications for permanent/durable catalog cards and performance standards for library bindings. The Laboratory is currently executing a contract jointly for the Council and the Library of Congress for the revision of the 1960

³⁴ In the First Annual Report, for the period ending June 30, 1957, it was said, ". . . the Council has taken advantage of the life-long enthusiasm of an outstanding documents-restoration expert (the late William J. Barrow) to commence study toward the betterment of the situation regarding the librarian's chief stock-in-trade—paper." I: 21.

specifications for permanent/durable book papers developed by the late Mr. Barrow with encouragement from the Council.

During the past year the Laboratory has conducted investigations on such subjects as the effect of storage temperature and humidity on paper, the potential of seven different polymers for strengthening weak papers, and deacidification of paper by gaseous diffusion. For the Library of Congress it tested papers used in certain government publications and those used in its binding and restoration shops. Specifications for a paper archive were prepared for the Council. A chapter on the aging of paper was contributed to a handbook of paper technology,⁸⁵ and a summary report of characteristics of book papers, 1507-1970, is in preparation for publication. In addition to continuing work on investigations already under way, the Laboratory during the next two years plans to work on, among other subjects, the suitability of various laminating films for protection of documents, improvements in bookbinding, problems connected with storage of microfilm, and characteristics of vegetable parchment.

The historical background and the present concern for paper are described in a three-part article by Verner W. Clapp, consultant to the Council and its former president, in *Scholarly Publishing*, the University of Toronto Press' journal for authors and publishers.⁸⁶

Preservation Research Office at Library of Congress An outcome of a 1967 reorganization at the Library of Congress was provision for the establishment there of a Preservation Research Laboratory, and the Council made a grant to the Library for the purchase of some of the needed equipment.⁸⁷ Operation of the Laboratory has been delayed by the long search for a qualified director, but this year one was appointed and equipment ordered. The Laboratory will engage in both practical and basic research relating not only to paper but also to adhesives, bookbindings, microfilm, motion picture film, and magnetic tape.

Imperial College of Science and Technology The disastrous floods which ravaged Florence in 1966 brought to light the fact that books bound in limp vellum prior to the 16th century stood up remarkably well under conditions which so seriously affected volumes otherwise bound. When it was decided to rebind in this medium some of the flood-damaged books

⁸⁵ Ann M. Carlton. "Aging of Paper." In *Handbook of Pulp and Paper Technology*, edited by Kenneth W. Britt. New York, Van Nostrand Reinhold Company, (1970). p. 709-714.

⁸⁶ Verner W. Clapp. "The story of permanent/durable book-paper, 1115-1970." *Scholarly Publishing* 2: 107-124, January; 229-245, April; 353-367, July 1971.

⁸⁷ XIV: 34.

in the Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale, it became apparent that the old technology, which began to degenerate after 1520, was no longer known or practiced. Knowledge of the old craft is desirable not only for restoration purposes but because it may have useful implications for modern binding practices. The Council has therefore made a grant to the Imperial College of Science and Technology in London for an analytical study of early limp vellum bindings, in regard to both materials and techniques, and some experimentation toward the improvement of modern methods.

Another investigation which also owes its origin to the Florentine floods is in the use of the scanning electron microscope to find the effects upon paper of mud, various deacidifying chemical reagents, and protective tissues. A published paper on the subject suggests that a whole new line of inquiry into the physics and chemistry of deacidification and lamination of paper may be opening up.³⁸ Certain other investigations at Imperial College, to which the Council had been giving support,³⁹ have been terminated.

VII COLLEGE LIBRARY PROGRAMS

The *14th Annual Report* described the background and circumstances that led to the establishment of the joint Council on Library Resources—National Endowment for the Humanities College Library Program.⁴⁰ The two organizations have set aside a sum of money for the support of selected innovative programs designed to bring the academic library into active partnership with the faculty in the education of undergraduates.

The first grants—matched by the recipients—went to Brown University, Dillard University, and Jackson State College for programs developed by the librarians in cooperation with administrative officers and faculty teams. A fourth grant to Wabash College was made by the Council alone, since the college may not accept Federal funds.

This fiscal year the Endowment and the Council have joined in making matching grants to three more institutions for their five-year programs: Eastern Michigan University, Ypsilanti; Hampshire College, Amherst, Massachusetts; and Washington and Lee University, Lexington, Virginia.

³⁸ Margaret Hey. "The Use of the Scanning Electron Microscope in Document Restoration Problems." *Restaurator* 1: 4, 233-244. 1970.

³⁹ XIII: 34.

⁴⁰ XIV: 14-15.

Eastern Michigan in its "Library Outreach" program is seeking to identify for the teaching faculty the contributions librarians are prepared to make to the students' learning, to encourage their working together to achieve this goal, and to demonstrate the role librarians can play in the motivation of students. An important feature of the program is special help to students from urban disadvantaged areas. The position of Orientation Librarian has been created to provide a more personal approach to student assistance and to work toward a closer library-faculty-student relationship.

Hampshire College, a new experimental liberal arts institution, is taking a novel approach to library orientation: trying to orient the library to the user instead of orienting the user to the library. Among features of the program are investigations of user patterns, a multi-media orientation program intended to instruct users in self-help, and the training of student reference assistants for service in and outside of the library. Incident to the project is the development of a range of video tape, film slides, and limited computer programs in support of a wide variety of user needs. These are aids which may be useful to other libraries as well.

The program at Washington and Lee involves cooperative interplay of administration and faculty guidance, student initiative, and library support with resources and service. A faculty member has been designated to serve as reference coordinator, devoting half of his professional time to developing and executing the program, which will involve initially only selected academic departments in the undergraduate college of arts and sciences. Each of these departments will name a liaison professor who will teach an intensive bibliographical course dealing specifically with library resources in the department's field. The program also provides for student representation.

These seven universities and colleges represent institutions of varying character, size, and location. Their projects may eventuate in model programs which can be adapted to other campuses. A model demonstration of another nature is that of the Engineering Library at M.I.T., which has been mentioned earlier in this report.

The Core Collection After several years of background preparation by members of its staff, the Council in 1969-70 completed formal arrangements with the American Library Association for preparation and publication of a catalog of a collection of "core" books—books which would represent the minimum body of titles essential in any adequate, well-balanced college library collection.⁴¹ The catalog is intended to make easier the burden of basic book selection, a time-consuming activity and one for which not all librarians have sufficient background.

⁴¹ XIV: 16-17.

Advisory and editorial committees have been established, an editor chosen, and offices established in Middletown, Connecticut, where *CHOICE*, the book review journal for libraries, is located. The catalog will list approximately 40,000 titles, with the data base derived in large part from Library of Congress MARC records. Sample page layouts for text and index have been prepared by the American Library Association's publishing department and preliminary discussions held with a manufacturer. Since the catalog as a whole will be prepared from machine-readable records, it will be possible to prepare later editions expeditiously and accurately.

Some Standard Reference Works The Council has this year made grants to update three previously published standard reference works. *American Library Resources: A Bibliographical Guide*, by Robert B. Downs, Dean of Library Administration at the University of Illinois, Urbana, is a guide to the research holdings of U.S. libraries, listing 5,578 printed library catalogs, union lists of various types of materials, calendars of archives and manuscripts, exhibition catalogs, and other keys to collections published up to 1951. A first supplement covering the years 1950-61 and listing 2,818 titles, was published in 1962 with assistance from the Council.⁴² The Second Decennial Supplement, also supported by the Council and to be published by the American Library Association, will add titles published since the first supplement.

Mary W. Chamberlin's *Guide to Art Reference Books* is a basic tool for those doing subject and bibliographic research in painting, sculpture, prints, architecture, and the decorative arts. It has also been useful to librarians building collections in these fields. But in the years since its appearance in 1959 there has been a large growth of public interest in the arts, resulting in the publication of a considerable volume of reference material. The Council has therefore made a grant to Miss Etta Arntzen, a fine arts librarian who assisted in the preparation of the original guide, for work toward a new edition.

Sources of Information in the Social Sciences, by Carl M. White of the University of California Library, San Diego, and collaborators, was published as recently as 1964. So rapidly do changes occur in this area, however, that a new edition is desirable. As planned, the second edition will contain a brief account of the literature on each subject, a select list of recommended titles basic to a library collection, and a longer general listing of reference materials and published sources covering that subject. It is expected that about 3,000 titles will be identified as the most important for a worker in the social sciences.

⁴² VII: 18.

The Council has also made a grant for the preparation of a manual for the use of slide librarians and curators by Mrs. Betty Jo Irvine, Fine Arts Librarian at Indiana University. The manual is expected to provide guidelines for the establishment, maintenance, staffing, and equipping of slide libraries.

VIII INTERNATIONAL LIBRARY AFFAIRS

Ideas, and books as one form of their embodiment, recognize no national boundaries. It is inevitable, therefore—and wholly desirable—that there should be an international exchange of ideas about library work and a common interest in shared problems. The years since World War II especially have seen a growing spirit of cooperation on the part of librarians in many areas of the world and a drive toward international standardization of cataloging and other practices.

Support for IFLA The International Federation of Library Associations, founded in 1927 and with headquarters now in The Hague, is a nongovernmental organization, with consultative status in UNESCO. It works closely with many international associations with allied interests. During recent years special efforts have been made to establish cooperative activities with the International Federation for Documentation whose concern with the information needs in the sciences complements the work of IFLA.

Although it has been a significant instrument for international cooperation, discussion, and action in library affairs, IFLA has not been financially strong enough to develop its potential. So that IFLA may play its proper role, the Council has made a grant to enable the organization to strengthen its administrative and staff operations while it restructures its dues schedules. At the end of the three-year grant period IFLA expects to be in a position to continue to operate at the level made possible by the grant.

In other action, the Council has allocated funds to IFLA for the establishment and support of a permanent secretariat for its Committee on Cataloguing for a similar period. The secretariat will initially be located in quarters made available by the British Museum. The work of the Committee during the past decade has resulted in valuable contributions toward the international standardization of cataloging and bibliographical description.

The new permanent secretariat, which is expected to become self-supporting, will serve as the center for discussion of international

coordination and standardization of cataloging rules and practices. It will assist in the establishment of an international system for the exchange of bibliographical information by providing needed liaison between IFLA sections and committees which deal with the same problems from differing points of view. The secretariat is also expected to be influential in the reduction of overlapping projects with their consequent waste of effort.

UNISIST (ICSU) UNISIST is the name given to a plan put forward by the International Council of Scientific Unions (ICSU) and UNESCO to create a world-wide science information system, covering primarily natural and technical sciences. UNISIST is now beginning to take positive shape. This year UNESCO and ICSU issued a report of a four-year inquiry by a joint Central Committee created to inquire into the feasibility of a world science information system.⁴⁸ The report concludes that a "world science information system, considered as a flexible network based on the voluntary cooperation of existing information services, is both necessary and feasible." An intergovernmental conference to discuss such a system was scheduled to be held at UNESCO House, Paris, in October 1971. Because of the implications for libraries the Council on Library Resources has been following these developments with interest, and a representative has attended various UNESCO meetings on the subject.

In addition to attending meetings of the International Federation of Library Associations and of UNESCO, members of the Council's staff have been present at the quadrennial International Congress on Reprography, in London, and the plenary session of Technical Committee 46 of the International Standards Organization, in Lisbon.

International Symposium The University of Uppsala observed the 350th anniversary of the founding of its library in April 1971 with an International Symposium on University Libraries. Travel funds provided by the Council enabled seven librarians from the United States and another from Canada to accept invitations to the meeting in Sweden. In several other instances, when funds were not otherwise available, the Council made travel grants to librarians with leadership roles to play at meetings abroad.

⁴⁸ *UNISIST: Study Report on the feasibility of a World Science Information System*: by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization and the International Council of Scientific Unions. Paris, Unesco, 1971. (vi), 161. 27cms. An abridged version has also been published: *UNISIST: Synopsis of the feasibility study on a World Science Information System*; by . . . UNESCO, Paris, 1971. 92 p. 21cms. See also: A. Wysocki and J. Tocatljan. "A World Science Information System." *Unesco Bulletin for Libraries* 25: 62-66. March-April 1971.

Oriental Studies The first International Congress of Orientalists was held in Paris in 1873. But it was not until the XXVIIth Congress, held in Ann Arbor, Michigan, in 1967 that the importance of libraries to Oriental studies was fully given recognition. At that meeting a library panel, planned as part of the Congress' program, was held and led to the formation of the International Association of Orientalist Librarians, which is developing into an important instrument of professional communication and cooperation. The XXVIIIth Congress met in Canberra in January 1971, and there the Association in its first major activity held a series of library seminars. Approximately a hundred librarians enrolled for the seminars, the majority of them from outside Australia. Attendance at some sessions numbered 140 as a result of the presence of additional Canberra librarians and visiting scholars. The meeting represented the largest gathering to date of orientalist librarians from Asia and the West. The Council, as it had for the Ann Arbor meeting,⁴⁴ made a grant (this time to the Australian National University) to enable a number of Asian librarians to attend the Congress. The grant also makes possible publication within the coming year of the papers presented at the library seminars.

Two Directories: Dr. Rita Benton, Music Librarian at the University of Iowa, is the author of a *Directory of Music Research Libraries*. Part I, *Canada and the United States*, and, Part II, *Thirteen European Countries*, were published in 1967 and 1970 respectively. A grant has been made to the University of Iowa to forward her preparation of a third volume covering music research libraries in France, Italy, Spain, and Portugal. The directory is a recognized project of the International Association of Music Libraries.

Dr. Patricia K. Grimsted, Visiting Associate Professor, American University, is the author of *Archives and Manuscript Repositories in the USSR; A Guide to Research and Bibliography of Published Reference Aids*, now in print and to be released as part of Columbia University's Russian Institute series. The National Endowment for the Humanities and the Council have made matching grants to assist her preparation of a companion volume, *Regional Archives and Manuscript Repositories in the USSR*.

⁴⁴ XI: 40; XII: 32.

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

Opinion of Independent Accountants

September 10, 1971

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

In our opinion, the accompanying statement of assets, liabilities and fund balance and the related statements of expenditures and income and source and application of funds (Exhibits I-III) present fairly the assets, liabilities and fund balance of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1971, and June 30, 1970, its expenditures and income and sources and applications of funds for the years then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles consistently applied. Our examinations of these statements were made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary in the circumstances.

PRICE WATERHOUSE & CO.

EXHIBIT I

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

STATEMENT OF ASSETS, LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

ASSETS	June 30	
	1971	1970
Cash	\$ 265,297	\$ 109,747
Investments		
Savings account	3,566	
Certificates of deposit, at cost of \$250,000 and \$950,000 plus accrued interest	250,109	958,102
Accrued royalty income receivable	5,771	
Grant receivable from The Ford Foundation (Note 1)	1,061,035	2,820,374
Prepaid expenses and deposits	4,630	6,338
	<u>\$1,590,408</u>	<u>\$3,894,561</u>
 LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE		
Grants and contracts payable	\$1,217,694	\$1,909,465
Fellowships payable	84,861	78,966
Accounts payable and accrued salaries, taxes and employee benefits	38,342	7,398
	<u>1,340,897</u>	<u>1,995,829</u>
Fund balance at beginning of year	1,898,732	3,925,865
Deduct—Expenditures less Income for the year (Exhibit II)	1,649,221	2,027,133
Fund balance at end of year (Note 2)	249,511	1,898,732
	<u>\$1,590,408</u>	<u>\$3,894,561</u>

EXHIBIT II

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

STATEMENT OF EXPENDITURES AND INCOME

EXPENDITURES	For the Year Ended June 30	
	1971	1970
Program expense		
Grants and contracts.....	\$1,346,692	\$1,670,980
Fellowships	55,290	51,395
Less: Adjustments resulting from excess allocations in grants and fellowships awarded.....	(149,982)	(106,316)
	<u>1,252,000</u>	<u>1,616,059</u>
Compensation and employee benefits.....	175,821	180,816
Consultants' fees and expenses.....	48,985	43,805
Travel	12,876	15,911
Other	2,552	476
	<u>1,492,234</u>	<u>1,857,067</u>
Administrative expense		
Compensation and employee benefits.....	136,963	142,752
Rent	21,580	20,683
Professional services	13,435	18,661
Travel and meetings.....	13,859	13,049
Furniture and equipment.....	3,515	21,435
Printing and duplication.....	8,441	7,334
Office and other expense.....	16,892	20,865
	<u>214,685</u>	<u>244,779</u>
	<u>1,706,919</u>	<u>2,101,846</u>
Income from investments.....	48,361	74,713
Income from royalties (Note 3).....	9,337	
	<u>57,698</u>	<u>74,713</u>
Expenditures less income.....	<u>\$1,649,221</u>	<u>\$2,027,133</u>

EXHIBIT III

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

STATEMENT OF SOURCE AND APPLICATION OF FUNDS

	For the Year Ended June 30	
	1971	1970
Cash provided by		
Receipts from Ford Foundation	\$1,759,339	\$1,179,626
Income from investments and royalties	59,920	89,633
Grant and fellowship refunds	2,931	27,760
	<u>1,822,190</u>	<u>1,297,019</u>
Cash applied to		
Program expense	2,164,660	1,543,472
Administrative expense	198,414	244,556
Employee travel advances		100
	<u>2,363,074</u>	<u>1,788,128</u>
Decrease in cash and investments during the year	(540,884)	(491,109)
Cash and investments, beginning of year	1,059,747	1,550,856
Cash and investments, end of year	<u>\$ 518,863</u>	<u>\$1,059,747</u>

NOTES

1) FORD FOUNDATION GRANTS

Effective July 1, 1971, The Ford Foundation has approved an additional \$5,000,000 grant to the Council for the continuation and expansion of the Council's program. The new grant agreement specifies that the remaining balance of the current grant and the new grant will be expended in substantial compliance with an annual budget of approximately \$2,000,000 for a three year period beginning July 1, 1971.

2) APPROPRIATIONS OF FUND BALANCE

At June 30, 1971, and June 30, 1970, \$1,698,797 and \$1,315,590, respectively, had been appropriated by the Board of Directors for specific grants and contracts and \$92,352 and \$68,180, respectively, had been allocated to the President for future grants and contracts of up to \$25,000 or additions to existing grants and contracts of up to \$5,000 each to be made at his discretion. The excess of appropriated amounts over the Fund balance at June 30, 1971, is attributable to appropriations made upon receipt of notification from The Ford Foundation of the grant which became effective July 1, 1971.

3) ROYALTIES

On October 10, 1969, the Council entered an agreement for the publication of "Handbook of Data Processing for Libraries" developed under its sponsorship. It is the Council's intention to use royalties received from sale of this publication to fund the preparation of revisions and supplements to the work.

EXHIBIT IV

STATEMENT OF GRANTS, CONTRACTS, AND
COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

Year Ended June 30, 1971

	Payable June 30, 1970	Grant Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1971
American Association for State and Local History					
Preparation of a manual on the collection and servicing of local history materials in libraries	\$ 31,215				\$ 31,215
American Association of Collegiate Business Schools, Inc.					
Survey of Business School Libraries....		\$ 2,000		\$ 2,000	
American Association of Law Libraries, Committee on Statistics					
Statistical survey of law library resources in the U.S. and Canada (revised project)	12,904			2,000	10,904
American Library Association					
Assistance in establishing a quarterly Journal of Information Science & Library Automation	4,391		\$ 5,403	(1,012)	
Book Catalog for a core collection for college libraries	265,336				265,336
Expenses of Committee on New Directions for ALA, 1969-70	7,547		4,811	2,736	
Preparation of a Second Decennial Supplement to American Library Resources: A Bibliographical Guide		4,000		2,000	2,000
Library Technology Program					
Projects of testing and standardization to August 31, 1967	28,726		4,804	12,547	11,375
Extension of support, Library Technology Program to August 31, 1970	52,780		51,343	1,437	
Conservation of Library Materials, Phase II	22,500			7,500	15,000
Director's Discretionary Fund, April 1, 1969—August 31, 1970	6,000				6,000
Evaluation of library catalog cards....		3,322	159	3,163	
An evaluation of microform readers for libraries available on the American market	3,940		1,662	2,278	
Etta Arntzen					
Revision of Guide to Art Reference Books		8,000		3,200	4,800
Association of Research Libraries					
Establishment of an Office of University Library Management Studies within ARL		130,000		45,000	85,000
National Serials Pilot Project—Partial Support		19,107		19,107	
A study of lighting requirements for libraries			295	(295)	
The Australian National University					
Assistance toward expenses of a library panel, 28th International Congress of Orientalists in Canberra, Australia, January 6-12, 1971		20,000		20,000	

	Payable June 30, 1970	Grant Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1971
W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, Inc. Operation of a laboratory for investiga- tions relative to the preservation of books and other library materials.....	\$ 124,791			\$ 102,606	\$ 22,185
Booz, Allen & Hamilton, Inc. To conduct a study of University Library organization and staffing at Columbia University		\$ 90,000		50,218	39,782
Columbia University The P.L. 480 Program in American Libraries	1,883			941	942
Dartmouth College Coordination of a program for producing microfilm editions of rare research materials		8,800		4,000	4,800
Federation of American Societies for Experimental Biology Development of criteria for quality con- trol of input in science information systems	2,500		\$ 1,183	1,317	
Imperial College of Science and Technology (London) Research on the conservation of library materials	50,160			13,540	36,620
Study of early limp vellum binding prac- tices for purposes of conservation, with possible implications for modern limp binding techniques		9,720		2,000	7,720
International Federation of Library Associations Establishment of a Permanent Secretariat for the IFLA Committee on Cataloging... To assist the International Federation of Library Associations in its effort to strengthen the organization.....		54,000		4,200	49,800
		100,000		8,000	92,000
Betty Jo Irvine To prepare and edit a Slide Library Manual		4,389		1,000	3,389
Levittown Public Library Test of an electronic book-theft detection system		8,990		6,000	2,990
Library of Congress Center for the coordination of foreign manuscript copying (continuation).....	14,595			7,298	7,297
Conversion of Retrospective Cataloging Records to Machine-Readable Form RECON (continuation)	105,151			95,572	9,579
Equipment for Preservation Research Office	48,550				48,550
Massachusetts Institute of Technology Project Intrex, 10/1/68-6/30/70.....	70,667			70,667	
Project Intrex, 7/1/70-6/30/71.....		400,000		300,000	100,000
Project Intrex—Model Engineering Library	99,750			67,000	32,750
Mathematica Study of the economics of university library operation, Phase I and Phase II..	15,000	17,500		21,000	11,500
R. A. Morgan Company Construction and testing of a prototype of a bibliographer's camera.....	1,500			1,500	

	Payable June 30, 1970	Grant Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1971
National Academy of Sciences					
Appraisal of library and information system research and experimentation involving computers	\$ 41,920			\$ 36,000	\$ 5,920
National Central Library (London)					
Continued publication and increased distribution of American Acquisitions Lists	11,500			10,500	1,000
National Endowment for the Humanities					
Continuation of the College Library Program	200,000			200,000	
Development and operational testing of a data management system at the University of Chicago Library; extension of present capability	400,000			400,000	
A new program of Cataloging in Publication		\$ 200,000		200,000	
Preliminary study to prepare a proposal for studying goals of library service		12,096		12,096	
Preparation of Regional Archives and Manuscript Repositories in the USSR: A Directory & Bibliography of Published Reference Aids		12,739		12,739	
Study of adult public library users in the Bedford-Stuyvesant Community		2,700		2,700	
To investigate the effectiveness of the public library as a center for independent study toward achieving a two-year college education (CLEP)		25,000		25,000	
Carol A. Nemeayer					
The Republishing Industry: Identification, description and analysis of scholarly book and journal reprint publishing	455				455
The Newberry Library					
Feasibility study for a catalog of historical maps in Midwestern collections: Phase I	1,350			1,000	350
New England Board of Higher Education					
Technical and user audit of the NELINET Cataloging Support Sub-System		24,000		10,000	14,000
The New York Public Library					
An experiment to determine the feasibility of putting NYPL Research Libraries retrospective and prospective catalogs on microfilm		10,000		2,000	8,000
North Carolina State Board of Higher Education					
Feasibility study of a state research depository library	3,500			3,500	
Ohio College Library Center					
Development of a computerized regional library system: implementation of a shared cataloging system	5,600			4,400	1,200
Ohio State University Research Foundation					
An institute on automated on line circulation system; evaluation, development, and use		1,534			1,534
Rice University					
A study of the use of microforms as a regional catalog		75,000	\$ 70,964	4,036	

	Payable June 30, 1970	Grant Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1971
Society of American Archivists, Special Projects Funds					
Toward the expenses of a committee to examine the programs of the Society of American Archivists	\$ 2,500	\$ 1,000			\$ 3,500
Tulane University Library					
Conversion of a computer-taped catalog to microfilm, and test of user acceptance	\$ 3,280	820		2,211	1,889
United States Book Exchange					
Financial assistance to the United States Book Exchange		48,450		10,000	38,450
University of California, San Diego					
2nd Edition of Sources of Information in the Social Sciences	4,910				4,910
University of California, Santa Cruz					
Development of a machine-manipulable classification scheme for slides in the sciences			\$ 9	(9)	
Publication of A Universal Slide Classifi- cation System with Automatic Indexing ..	3,370		8	3,362	
University of Lancaster					
Fundamental reseach on factors affecting the use of library services		37,500		9,000	28,500
University of Iowa					
A Directory of Music Research Libraries in France, Italy, Portugal, and Spain		1,425			1,425
University of North Carolina (on behalf of American National Standards Institute Sectional Committee Z39)					
Development of standards in library work and documentation	40,850			10,000	30,850
University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia					
Proposal for a Middle Atlantic States- University of Pennsylvania Archive of Medieval Manuscripts on film—Stage II ..	2,000			2,000	
Vanderbilt University on behalf of the Joint University Libraries					
Establishment of a model research and development unit	159,007			36,300	122,707
Various*					
Fund for Foreign Librarians to visit the United States	5,000			250	4,750
Guide to resources of a consortium of seven Middle Atlantic University Libraries	2,200			314	1,886
Travel grants to attend meetings abroad ..	4,637	10,100		10,742	3,995
Travel grant for the Filming Standards Subcommittee of Rare Books Conference on Facsimiles		2,000		1,161	839
Wabash College					
To increase the effectiveness of the library in the educational program of Wabash College-College Library Program ..	50,000			7,500	42,500
Subtotal, Grants, Contracts and Council- administered Projects					
	\$1,909,465	\$1,346,692	\$140,641	\$1,897,822	\$1,217,694
Fellowship Program*					
	78,966	55,290	9,341	40,054	84,861
Total, Grants, Contracts, and Council-administered Projects					
	\$1,988,431	\$1,401,982	\$149,982	\$1,937,876	\$1,302,555

* Council-administered project

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The sketch of the scholar at his book-wheel, which appears on the front cover, is adapted from an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine*, Paris, 1588. The original engraving was reproduced in the Council's Third and subsequent annual reports.

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